

636 genes (2 fold change)

808 genes (2 fold change)

493 genes (2 fold change, FDR 0.05)

486 genes (2 fold change, FDR 0.05)



*Mtb* 18b, streptomycin depletion, 2 weeks



"Dormancy regulon" (Voskuil *et al.* 2003, Voskuil *et al.* 2004)



Reactive nitrogen (Ohno *et al.* 2003)



Microaerophilic (NRP1) (Muttucumaru *et al.* 2004)



Anaerobic (NRP2) (Muttucumaru *et al.* 2004)



Hypoxia, 7 days (Rustad *et al.* 2008)



Reduced oxygen (Bacon *et al.* 2004)



Macrophage (Rhode *et al.* 2007)



Macrophage (Homolka *et al.* 2010)



Nutrient depletion (Betts *et al.* 2002)



Nutrient depletion (Hampshire *et al.* 2004)



SDS stress (Manganelli *et al.* 2001)



Phosphostarvation (Rifat *et al.* 2009)